

REPORT:

*A4.1.4: Current state of the art of
modularity and heterogenous
integration of microfluidic systems*

Work package 4

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1. Scope

This report is based on the input from A4.1.1-A4.1.3 providing an overview of the latest methods and techniques used for composition and heterogenous combination of microfluidic systems and functional components. As a result, we provide a document sharing the state of the art in creating integrated microfluidic systems.

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A4.1.4 M21	Using input from A4.1.1-A4.1.3, microfluidic with support from INESC MN and EnablingMNT will produce a report on the current state of the art of modularity and heterogenous integration of microfluidic systems and components. The report will be shared with relevant standardisation groups such as ISO/TC48/WG3 and WG5, ISO/TC229, CEN/TC332/WG7.	microfluidic , INESC MN, EnablingMNT

2. Introduction

The goal of assembling a modular microfluidic system should be to make it easier for customers and especially newbies in microfluidics to select, combine and install different microfluidic units (e.g. control devices like pumps, flow units) for their specific needs and to operate it in a targeted way. Unfortunately, an overview of the needs defined by the customer (developing the set-up) combined with the opportunities available (components, equipment, modularization concepts by suppliers) is lacking so far. To reach democratization in microfluidics, providing a matrix including well described microfluidic components for seamless modular and integrative assembling is essential.

First of all, a list of basic performance parameters, focusing on the integration and combination of microfluidic components, was created. By doing this, groups referring to well-defined classes of microfluidic products can be defined, as well as the requirement of connection systems for each product class. Moreover, to monitor and meter processes in online tests in a noninvasive, nondestructive manner by integration of sensing and control elements is highly attractive.

3. Defining essential parameters for microfluidic set-up elaboration

The partners of MFMET project identified three major performance parameters which set a basis in designing a microfluidic device or developing a microfluidic application. Those parameters are pressure drop, temperature and chemical resistance of the device. These three parameters play a significant role in designing a microfluidic device for different applications. Some applications require high-pressure flow inside a device, such as using inertial flows (higher Reynolds number), whereas some applications require a minimum increase in temperature during the operation. For example, experiments with biological samples (cells, DNA, enzymes, etc.) should prevent temperature rise to avoid potential degradation or other detrimental effects on the samples. Similarly, microfluidic devices need to be chemically resistant when dealing with applications that involve the use of chemicals. Additionally, some applications require the device to be both heat and chemical resistant as well as withstand high pressure. For instance, high throughput sorting of biological cells may involve the use of electrokinetics under pressure-driven flow. In this regard, the rise of temperature is expected due to joule heating. Corrosion of the device could also be expected due to pH changes as well as the occurrence of electrolysis. Therefore, users need to choose above mentioned parameters wisely before designing the chip.

4. Heterogenous and modular integration of microfluidic components and devices

The participants of discussion groups led by key suppliers of microfluidic components concluded that heterogenous integration is hardly suitable for standardization since it is done entirely in one factory. However, modular integration is very much in need of standardization, as the parts from different suppliers need to fit to each other.

The microfluidic connector was identified as a key aspect for modular integration of microfluidic devices since the fluidic interconnection by tubes and connectors is mostly used. Due to high diversity and lacking standardization of microfluidic connectors, a seamless transfer to an integrated modular microfluidic device is difficult or even components and devices turn out incompatible. The handling for non-experts is therefore quite difficult.

To solve this, a standardized connector class should be established to enable seamless connection of microfluidic components and devices for developing integrated systems in a “plug-and play” mechanism. For converting this need, a hotspot application area was defined and requirements for an ideal connector were set. A pressure below 2 bar, temperature between 4-50°C and a “middle flow rate” between (1-100) µl/min were detected as requirements covering main market segments like research and analytical instrumentation.

Of course, this approach used to propose an ideal connector for standardization gives further room for follow-up designs considering parameters like pressure ranges, gases, or multiple ports. In addition to the basic parameters, further requirements were formulated, like the biocompatibility, the reusability, the leak tightness, the suitability for rigid tubing and the lowest footprint possible.

After the forgoing conclusion was reached, one-one and group brainstorming sessions were held with key suppliers and we came to the conclusion that:

- 1) Heterogenous integration is hardly suitable for standardisation as it is done completely in one factory. Modular integration however is very much in need for standardisation as parts from different suppliers need to fit to each other.
- 2) A key aspect of modular integration of microfluidic devices is of course the way how fluid is transferred from one component or device to another (pumps, valves, chips, etc). In a stand-alone setup this is done by tubes and microfluidic connectors. This kind of set up is used often by researchers and developers and may lead to an integrated system when the development work is finished.
- 3) Unfortunately, there is no standard in microfluidic connectors and existing microfluidic connectors are difficult to handle for non-experts.
- 4) Preferable, one would use the same component in the development phase (stand-alone setup) as in the final phase (modular integrated). Therefore an ideal microfluidic connector should provide a seamless path towards further integration.
- 5) No existing microfluidic connector can fill that role, although the number of different connector types is, unfortunately, high. Due to that diversity they are incompatible with each other.
- 6) The high number of different connectors, makes it very difficult for users to connect microfluidic components and devices.

5. Current state of the art for heterogenous sensor integration

In task A4.1.2 a literature review was provided giving a comprehensive overview of solutions and expertise regarding the integration and/or assembly of components into a functional microfluidic system. Those components encompass all compounds for sensor technology, electronics, data processing and further. Sensors for sensitive system parameters like O₂, CO₂, temperature or pH extend the analytical opportunities. Sensor integration on chip is made possible by the efforts in microelectronics and micro-/nanofabrication as well as solutions in compatibility between different substrate materials and sensors. Especially online metering or monitoring is highly attractive, although challenging due to complexity in miniaturization and maintenance of sensitivity. Moreover, combining sensing and control elements with microfluidics has a special potential in the development of self-contained portable laboratories. On the one hand, this potential is highly driven and supported by the invention of open-source microcontrollers, which deliver easy-to-use development environments for fully integrated lab-on-a-chip devices. On the other hand, microfluidic-based handling platforms, esp. manufactured in polymers, provide an ideal basis for portable lab-on-a-chip solutions. The manufacturing process in chip fabrication provides high reproducibility and scalability as well as accuracy in dimensions. Most often, micro-patterning like lithography or etching and bonding via ozone plasma or corona is used to create functional channel structures on microfluidic chip devices. Reversible (pressure driven forces) bonding allows mainly and repeated access to the channels or chip chambers and is reusable. In contrast, permanent bonding is often limited esp. in multiplexing but shows a reduced risk of leakages. Lately, different strategies were proposed for assembling like interconnection of layered modules through micromachined interlocking pins (Gonzales). As reviewed, modular chip structuring is done by stacking different functional layers of thermoplastic polymers or using various strategies of alignment like hemispherical pin-in-hole/pin-in-slot- and plate-plate lap joint. Further advantages are using electronic modules like PCBs enabling individual module assembling. Combining hybrid technologies like sensors is challenging because manufacturing processes vary depending on their application area and what they sense for.

Table 1 summarizes different sensing techniques with their advantages and disadvantages for the detection of a range of analytes using the most common transducers.

Table 1. Different examples of sensing techniques with their advantages and disadvantages [8]

Transducer	Technique	Advantages	Disadvantages
Electrochemical	Amperometric [43,44]	Simplicity, miniaturization, low cost	Need redox elements to enhance the current production; time consuming; sensitive to the surrounding environment
	Potentiometric [45,46]	Real-time detection; the possibility of continuous analysis on different analytes	Sensitive to the surrounding environment; time consuming; sensitive to temperature
	Impedimetric [47,48]	Simplicity and real-time detection	Sensitive to the surrounding environment; bulky devices required; require theoretical stimulation for data analysis
Optical	Surface plasmon resonance (SPR) [49,50]	Real-time detection; reliable, high sensitivity	Sensitive to the surrounding environment; surface modification as one of the main challenges; bulky optical devices required
Mechanical	Cantilever [51,52]	Real-time detection; ability to detect more than one analyte with high sensitivity	Sensitive to the surrounding environment; sensitive to temperature; bulky devices required
	Quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) [53,54]	Real-time detection; simplicity; high compatibility with point-of-care (POC) devices	Sensitive to the surrounding environment; sensitive to temperature and stress

The potential for developing discrete sensors is infinitely varied and diverse. It becomes difficult, if not impossible, to predict what packaging approaches can be designed, or how these devices operate as discrete devices while being integrated with other electronics functions in a signal chain. This task is further compounded by the fact that each application may have different operational environments

and performance requirements. For example, when it comes to operational environment, inertial MEMS sensors must be mounted on the moving element of the system, which is quite different than a gas sensor wherein packaging must have a physical opening for gas to interact with the sensing element. Furthermore, if we consider only inertial MEMS-based sensors, using them for automotive applications requires high reliability, repeatability, and long life; using them for consumer handheld applications requires lower cost, a short life cycle, higher mechanical reliability challenges, and relatively lower thermal challenges.

The materials currently used in fabricating sensors and future needs are presented in Table 2 for chemical, electrochemical, acoustic, optical, and ultrasonic sensors.

Table 2. Materials and future needs for sensors and actuators [21]

Sensor type	Examples of main future needs
<i>Chemical sensors</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Polysilicon (doped and undoped), single crystal silicon • Silicon nitride • Low stress nitride • Silicon oxide • Single crystal silicon (SOI) • Anti-stiction coatings (siloxanes primarily) • Wear coatings (e.g. MoS₂) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low stress materials • Low coefficient of thermal expansion mismatch • Coatings – anti-stiction, anti-wear, anticorrosion, charge elimination
<p><i>Some of the drivers for motion sensor materials are to prevent the mechanical devices from sticking to the substrate, and materials that have a good CTE match to prevent unwanted bending and stress.</i></p>	
<i>Electrochemical sensors</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Magnetoelastic • Potentiometric (Pt/PtO₂, W/W₂O₃, Pb/PbO₂, Ir/IrO₂) • ZnO • Silicon, silicon oxide • Aluminum electrodes • Nickel heaters • Aluminum, Alumina • Platinum, TiO₂ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Polyaniline • Boron-doped silicon nano-wires (SiNWs) • Nanoparticles for specific gas attraction (increase surface sites for adsorption) • Highly selective, high-sticking coefficient materials
<p><i>Some of the drivers for chemical sensor materials are to facilitate chemical reactions in a repeatable and stable way.</i></p>	
<i>Acoustic sensors/actuators</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Polysilicon • Silicon oxides • Silicon nitride • Piezoelectrics (PZT, AlN, SiN_x) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Piezoelectrics that don't fatigue at low temperature • Lead-free piezoelectrics (e.g. KNN) • Layer thickness increases for PZT, KNN (5-50 μm with good performance and high throughput)

- Development of magnetostrictive actuator materials
- Development of electroresistive low power materials

Some of the drivers for acoustic sensor/actuator materials such as speakers are to facilitate controlled motion to move/detect sound. Materials that do not fatigue are also important due to the large number of cycles the devices go through. Several different sensor/actuator types may be found – capacitive typically making use of silicon membranes, piezoelectric sensors make use of piezoelectric materials such as PZT and AlN, etc.

Optical sensors/actuators

- Au, Pt, Pd, Ti
- Silicon, optical glass, AR coatings, glass to metal, bonding in packaging
- NiCr strain gage, Cr, Au, silicon nitride, silicon oxides
- Al, Al alloys
- SAW, BAW: piezo (e.g. LiTaO3)
- FBAR ZnO or AlN
- Thin film layers for adhesion and diffusion for mirror metal
- Layers do not change mirror shape over temperature
- Thin film layers for adhesion and diffusion for mirror metal
- High quality LNO deposition
- Lead free optical glass (develop new processes for this new material)
- Low outgassing materials for optical sensors
- Electrets – low power
- Piezoelectrics that do not fatigue at low temperature
- Layer thickness increases for PTZ, KNN (5-50 μm with good performance and high throughput)

Some of the drivers for optical sensor/actuator materials are to create flat and reflective surfaces that do not change their shape and that have the appropriate optical properties. Material coatings with the correct properties are also important in optical MEMS

Ultrasonics and RF MEMS

- PMUT-ultrasonic transducers: PZT, AlN, SiN, silicon
- CMUT-ultrasonic transducers: SiN, silicon
- MEMS switch: precious metals for contacts – Au, Ag, Pt, Pd, Ru, Rh, Os
- PMUT-ultrasonic transducers:
 - Doped-AlN with higher piezo performance
 - Piezos with higher process stability, reproducibility, homogeneity, lower deposition cost
- CMUT-ultrasonic transducers: low stress and excellent membrane thickness homogeneity control over the substrate
- MEMS switch: RF MEMS switch materials for contacts

Some of the drivers for these materials are to create structures that create/sense ultrasonic waves and have repeatable, optimized properties that are manufacturable. In piezoelectric devices, materials with a good piezoelectric transfer coefficient are prized. PZT has been routinely used but has been supplanted by AlN due to the need to refrain from creating devices using lead. AlN has been typically doped with Scandium to increase its performance. In RF MEMS switches, the development of reliable contact materials has increased the commercialization of certain types of switches.

The availability of accurate materials properties is critically important for obtaining correct device performance simulation results. As new materials are brought online, their characterization is important to simulation success. Current issues include characterizing new materials used in the packaging, chemical and biosensors.

For well characterized processes and mature devices, simulations and experimental results often agree, but for modeling of new types of devices, the physics may not be well understood, as in some biodevices.

6. Executive summary - Workshop Integration of sensors and electronics in microfluidics - challenges and opportunities – March 7 and 8 of 2024

To check our ideas about the integration of microfluidic systems, a workshop was held on March 7 and 8 in Leuven, Belgium. The workshop was hosted by imec and supported by the Microfluidics Association and attended by over 100 participants. Here below the conclusions of this workshop.

Technologies in development by the microfluidic community are as diverse as its applications, but there are several technical challenges shared by most of the microfluidic community: In the first place connected to the choice of materials: 1) interaction of liquid and wetted materials (leaching, cytotoxicity, etc.) 2) How to control the surface of the materials and how to qualify it. 3) Stress introduced during packaging caused by differences in thermal expansion.

All developers of microfluidic devices wrestle with the lack of standard reliability tests, for instance the lack of qualified fast leakage test, lack of qualified accelerated reliability tests. At the basis of such tests are fault modes of microfluidic devices. An overview of common fault modes and how to prevent them happening would be very welcome. In relation to that: design for manufacturing was suggested.

Interconnections, standard interfaces. ISO 22916:2022 Microfluidic devices - Interoperability requirements for dimensions, connections and initial device classification up in the roadmap of ISO 22916:2022 [Microfluidic devices] is coming up for revision and a consultation period for revision will be started soon. Questions to be answered: are the chip sizes small enough to cover also future trends? Should we add agreement reached about sensor footprints for top down assembly concepts?

In respect to sensors: how to integrate them efficiently with microfluidics? Can we measure more than one parameter with one sensor? Can we have multiple sensors in one package or multiple sensors in one chip?

For integration of silicon and microfluidics, the IC factories will likely provide a first line packaging, where after that package can be integrated by adding a microfluidic “fan out” to overcome the size differences between silicon components and microfluidic parts.

In terms of integration a tendency towards to stacked or top down approaches in assembly is becoming apparent.

Reliable cleaning and sterilization techniques need to be developed / qualified for microfluidics.

Standardization in microfluidics is advancing well but not (yet) compatible with silicon wafer industry technologies.

Several speakers stressed the need for more ecofriendly design, either by using biodegradable materials or biobased materials or by designing modularly or by developing devices that are reusable.

There seems to be a trend towards modular approaches in microfluidics, but there also seems to be interesting opportunities in heterogenous integration of sensor functionalities.

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